

Past to Future

Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

Global datasets of ocean circulation and ocean temperature

Deliverable 12.1 | February 2026

University of Durham

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OUTPUT SUMMARY	
Deliverable Name	Global datasets of ocean circulation and ocean temperature
Deliverable Number	D12.1
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package No	WP12
Lead Beneficiary	University of Durham
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Due Date (month)	February 2026
Delivery Date	2026.02.28
Abstract	Records of ocean temperatures for high and low CO2 climate states have been reviewed and compiled drawing on existing data synthesis efforts. We have reviewed and synthesized stable isotope data as well as proxies for ocean temperature response and circulation changes.
Related Objective(s)	O12.1 - Quantify ocean temperature and circulation responses to high and low CO2 climate states.
Related Task(s)	T12.1 - Review and update existing global datasets of ocean circulation and ocean temperature at annual to millennial scales [M1-12]

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of main changes
21.01.2026	0.1	Erin McClymont, Anna Cutmore, Kasia Sliwinska, Louise Sime	First draft ready for review
22.01.2026		Helle Astrid Kjaer, Martin Ziegler	Feedback received
27.01.2026	0.2	Erin McClymont, Anna Cutmore	Final draft ready
16.02.2026		Anna von der Heydt, Stefanie Ypma	Feedback received
20.02.2026	0.3	Anna Cutmore	Deliverable ready for submission

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1. Summary

This document provides an overview of the review and synthesis of ocean circulation and ocean temperature data undertaken by Workpackage 12 of the Horizon Europe Past to Future (P2F) project during Months 1-12. In this time, U.Durham has completed the identification, compilation, and review of globally distributed sea-surface temperature (SST) records spanning the the Mid-Holocene (MH; 6.5-5.5 ka), Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; 23-19 ka), and late Pliocene (3.3-3.0 Ma). These records include SST reconstructions from both geochemical proxies and faunal assemblages. For the **MH** we have identified 1001 faunal assemblage and geochemical proxy records from 778 cores. For the **LGM** we have identified 1416 faunal assemblage and geochemical proxy records from 1098 cores. For the **Pliocene** we have identified 127 geochemical proxy records from 90 cores. To ensure that we can provide the modelers with clear descriptors of data quality, U.Durham and BAS have in discussion with P2F Workstream 1 assessed the suitability of these records for model evaluation and tuning. The assessment carried out by Workstream 2 (Workpackage 12) considered the robustness of each record's age model, the SST reconstruction methodology and associated uncertainties. Site location has also been included for quality control since it impacts whether the site is representative of local or regional conditions. In turn, site location influences both proxy uncertainties and model skill. The first compilations have been provided to the data portal (Workpackage 7) and will continue to be actively revised by Workpackage 12 as new data emerges from Past2Future work and external publications.

2. Evidence of accomplishment

2.1 Introduction | Background of the deliverable

The oceans are a critical part of Earth’s climate system, responsible for storing and redistributing heat through a suite of currents and water masses which record circulation at the sea surface and at depth (Talley, 2003). In turn, ocean circulation patterns influence the carbon cycle, the hydrological cycle, and how both sea ice and ice sheets advance and retreat across a range of timescales (from years to millions of years). Reconstructing changes in ocean properties in the past allows us to assess the rates and amplitudes of climate variability and better understand climate drivers and impacts. Using sediments which have accumulated over millions of years on the seafloor, we use a range of techniques to reconstruct changes in ocean temperatures and circulation for climates which are outside the conditions observed in the instrumental record (e.g., warmer-than-present or colder-than-present) (e.g. Tierney et al., 2020; McClymont & Ho et al., 2025)). Our measurements are “proxies”: indirect records of past climate variables. One of our proxies uses the relative abundance of fossils present within the sediments, which can reconstruct temperature, nutrients, sea ice etc (e.g. Kucera et al., 2005a). Another technique tracks changes in water temperature recorded by geochemical signals (e.g., lipid distributions in plankton cells or trace metal contents in their shells) (e.g. Tierney et al., 2020). We can also trace water masses at the sea surface or in the deep ocean (e.g., deep waters which have flowed from the North Atlantic region can have different characteristics from those coming from the South, which are recorded by changes to shell geochemistry) (e.g. Ravelo and Andreasen, 2000).

The palaeo-environmental data from the oceans can be used in two ways: to create time-series of ocean temperature and circulation changes at specific locations over time (Figure 1a), and to map the spatial distribution of ocean properties for important “snapshots” of the past (Figure 1b). It is these same snapshots, or “time slices”, which are modelled by the comprehensive Earth System Models at a global scale (cESMs; Workpackages 3, 4, 5). There has been concern that the cESMs being used to project the future might be too tightly constrained by the instrumental era, and so may not be as effective when the climate system shifts to warmer-than-present or colder-than-present climates. The palaeo-environmental record provides data against which models of past climate can be evaluated (Figure 1b). A key aim of Past2Future (P2F) is to use these improved models to more robustly project future climates.

Figure 1. a) Timeseries of alkenone-based SSTs (°C) from core MD02-2588 in the Indian-Atlantic Ocean gateway, spanning 40-2 ka (Romero et al., 2015). The Mid-Holocene (MH; 5.5-6.5 ka) and Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; 19-23 ka) timeslices are highlighted; b) Mapped SST anomalies for the LGM time slice for proxy data (dots) and cESM outputs compared to the pre-industrial, adapted from Lunt et al. 2024.

A key component of Workstream 2 is the facilitation of access to the most up-to-date data syntheses, including details of data quality control, via the dedicated Data Portal (Workpackage 7). All Workpackage 12 data and our assessments are being made available through the Data Portal, where version control also means that we can update our data synthesis as new data emerges or new considerations for data quality are published.

The time-slice ocean data that Workpackage 12 provides through WP7 to the modelers will be used in two ways: to evaluate model performance through data-model comparison (Task 3.3) and to tune the cESMs to create models

informed by palaeo-environmental data (Task 5.2). P2F has identified intervals of warmer-than-present and colder-than-present climates for data-model comparison and tuning (Mid-Holocene, Last Glacial Maximum, late Pliocene glacial-interglacial cycles). Workpackage 12 is identifying, compiling, evaluating and synthesizing the existing data for ocean temperature and ocean circulation (Task 12.1). The review outlined here for Task 12.1 also allows us to identify critical locations and time intervals where new analyses (Tasks 12.2, 12.3) will lead to a significant improvement in the data available to modelers (Tasks 3.2 and 5.2).

A challenge in data-model comparison is that the palaeoclimate proxy data do not map linearly onto the physical climate variables provided by the models. For example, stable isotope data from surface ocean microfossils includes both temperature and salinity components, whose contributions may vary over time and thus impact confidence in the temperature signal. One of the new capabilities that P2F aims to add to ESMs is the ability to model water isotopes (Task 1.2, Task 2.1), which can be directly compared to the proxy data we synthesize in Workpackage 12 (Task 3.3). Given the importance of providing the highest-quality data for the P2F “Grand Challenge” of tuning and developing the cESMs under paleoclimate conditions (Task 5.2), in Task 12.1 we have also reviewed the range of factors which impact proxy data quality and uncertainty (detailed in Section 2.2, Methodology).

2.2 Content of the deliverable

Methodology

Given the importance of data quality for data-model comparison and model tuning (Task 3.3 and Task 5.2) we have identified which modern calibrations are used to convert geochemical measurements or species groups into quantified temperatures and the associated scatter in those relationships. We have reviewed the quality of the age models which underpin the ocean temperature or circulation data, since a poorly constrained time slice could introduce additional variability to the record, or a record with only a few data points may fail to capture the range of variability. Finally, the position of the record is also important, since coastal sites can be challenging to model and can introduce wider scatter in the calibrations, thus increasing the data uncertainties.

All published global sea-surface temperature (SST) records spanning the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; 23-19 ka), the Mid-Holocene (MH; 6.5-5.5 ka), and the late Pliocene (3.3-3.0 Ma) were mapped (Fig. 2, 3 and 4). These syntheses bring together SST records reconstructed using both geochemical proxies (U^{K}_{37} index, TEX_{86} paleothermometer, planktonic foraminifera Mg/Ca ratios, and the Long-chain Diol Index and faunal assemblages (foraminifera, diatoms, dinocysts, coccoliths, and radiolarians). To meet Task 12.1 “Review and update existing global datasets of ocean circulation and ocean temperature at annual to millennial scales” we reviewed all previously published syntheses of SST records from the MH, LGM and Pliocene (detailed in the next paragraph). These datasets were updated by incorporating newly published records, including those generated since the original syntheses and those using SST reconstruction techniques not previously represented.

For the MH, we built on a previously published synthesis by Hessler et al., (2014), adding SSTs reconstructed using TEX_{86} , the Long-chain Diol Index and diatom and radiolarian assemblages, as well as SST records published since 2014. For the LGM, we built on previously published syntheses (i.e. Kucera et al., 2005a; Kucera et al., 2005b; Barker et al., 2005; Meland et al., 2005; Barrows & Juggins, 2005; Gersonde et al., 2005; Rosell-Mele et al., 2004; Tierney et al., 2020), including the Long-chain Diol Index, faunal assemblage records published since 2005, and all SST records published since 2020. For the Pliocene, we built on previously published syntheses by McClymont & Ho et al. (2023) and Tierney et al. (2025), adding SST records published since 2024. For stable isotope data, published data sets and previous syntheses were used for data-model comparisons in WP1 (e.g. Gao et al., 2025; Comas-Bru et al., 2020). The PlioMioVAR working group (including U.Durham) had also compiled and reviewed available stable carbon isotope and stable oxygen isotope data, using the same protocols as for the PlioVAR SST data. For the Pliocene snapshot, maps and ocean cross-sections of stable isotope data have been created for the Atlantic Ocean basin. These have been directly compared to a selection of model outputs to assess model

performance and identify proxy limitations, contributing to Task 3.3 which seeks to develop data-model comparison for cESMs. This work is under review, led by the PlioMioVAR steering committee chair and her team (Duong et al., under review, detailed in Outputs section below).

The new work to compile SST records has proceeded as follows. For each record, we compiled the following information: author(s) name, publication DOI, database DOI, core name, core location (Ocean, Region, Zone), time frame of the full record (ka), resolution of the record (years), proxy used to reconstruct SST record, technique used to produce the age model, details of corresponding d18O record from same core.

During the P2F General Assembly, we held discussions with modelling groups from Bristol, Leeds and Utrecht (and partner NCAR) on how to manage sites, prioritise information, and distinguish data suitable for data-model comparison from that used for model tuning. To provide the modelling community with a set of recommended records, an assessment framework was developed and applied to all MH and LGM records to evaluate their suitability for inclusion in the P2F database. During General Assembly break-out sessions, concerns were raised regarding coastal sites; therefore, the first screening step involved removing sediment cores recovered from shallow water depths and those located in close proximity to the coastline.

The second stage of the MH and LGM assessment addressed the record's age model by providing a chronozone for each record (a qualitative classification indicating the confidence level of the assigned age model for a sedimentary record) based on the following criteria, which is adapted from that of the 2005 MARGO project (Kucera et al., 2005a). Records with age models under chronozone 1 or 2 will be included in the P2F database. Due to differences in the age control methods for the Pliocene, a separate set of assessment criteria will be developed. At this stage, all records which met the age control criteria of the PlioVAR working group are included (ages based on oxygen-isotope ratios or paleomagnetic reversals, detailed in McClymont & Ho et al., 2023).

MH Chronozone Criteria:

Chronozone 1: Samples with at least one radiometric date within the MH interval (6.5 – 5.5 ka), such as U/Th dates or reservoir-corrected 14 C-yr dates, or annually counted layers extending through the interval

Chronozone 2: Chronologic control based on two bracketing radiometric dates of any kind within the interval 2-10 ka, or by correlation of non-radiometric data to similar regional records that have been dated to match the level 1 protocol (for example, d18O stratigraphy).

Chronozone 3: Chronologic control based on other stratigraphic constraints (for example, a regional lithologic index such as %CaCO₃) that are correlated to similar records dated elsewhere to match the level 2 protocol.

Chronozone 4: Sites without chronozone assignment and does not indicate sites with low chronological confidence.

LGM Chronozone Criteria:

Chronozone 1: Samples with at least two radiometric dates within the LGM interval (23 – 19 ka), such as U/Th dates or reservoir-corrected 14 C-yr dates or annually counted layers extending through the interval

Chronozone 2: Chronologic control based on two bracketing radiometric dates of any kind within the interval 12–30 ka (i.e., within marine oxygen-isotope stage 2), or by correlation of non-radiometric data to similar regional records that have been dated to match the level 1 protocol (for example, d18O stratigraphy).

Chronozone 3: Chronologic control based on other stratigraphic constraints (for example, a regional lithologic index such as %CaCO₃) that are correlated to similar records dated elsewhere to match the level 2 protocol.

Chronozone 4: Sites without chronozone assignment and does not indicate sites with low chronological confidence

Results

Stable isotope data-model comparisons:

For the stable isotope data-model comparisons (Task 1.2), U.Durham (with U.Leeds) have used existing data syntheses as noted above to assess isotope-enabled model performance, showing that while the overall structure of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation is reproduced in the Pliocene, there are differences in the distribution of important water masses especially in the deep Atlantic Ocean (Duong et al. in prep.). BAS (with U.Durham) has also reviewed isotope-enabled model performance for the simulation of water isotopes related to changes in SST and sea-ice extent (Sime et al., 2025).

SST compilations:

For the SST data, U.Durham identified the key sites relevant to P2F and assessed which of these met the chronozone criteria outlined above. For the MH we identified a total of 1001 faunal assemblage and geochemical proxy records from 778 cores (Figure 2) expanding on previous synthesis (Hessler et al., 2014) by including SSTs reconstructed using TEX_{86} , Long-chain Diol Index, diatom and radiolarian assemblages and records published since 2014. 142 of these cores were removed due to shallow depths or close proximity to the coastline. Of the remaining cores, 273 had multiproxy SST records. This builds on previous syntheses by including SSTs reconstructed using the Long-chain Diol Index (17 records), TEX_{86} (37 records) and diatom and radiolarian assemblages (63 records), as well as 134 records from Mg/Ca, $U^{K_{37}}$, foraminifera and dinoflagellate SST records published since Hessler et al. (2014).

For the LGM, U.Durham identified a total of 1416 faunal assemblage and geochemical proxy records from 1098 cores (Figure 3) with 82 of these cores removed due to shallow depths or close proximity to the coastline. Of the remaining cores, 454 had multiproxy SST records. This builds on previous syntheses by including SSTs reconstructed using the Long-chain Diol Index (10 records), geochemical records published since the Tierney et al., 2020 synthesis (38 new records) and faunal records published since the MARGO database (67 new records).

For the Pliocene, U.Durham built on the previously published PlioVAR synthesis by McClymont & Ho et al. (2023), and Pliocene synthesis by Tierney et al. (2025), and included newly published records. The PlioVAR group excluded records which did not meet their age control or sampling resolution, but these were included in a more recent synthesis by Tierney et al. (2025). We have merged the PlioVAR and Tierney syntheses, and include newly published records, with the different age control/resolution considerations flagged in the dataset. Our dataset includes 127 geochemical records from 90 cores with 28 of these cores having multi-proxy records. Six of these records were published since Tierney et al. (2025) and seven are new high-resolution unpublished records. The dominance of single-proxy sites and the sparse distribution of data in some regions means that to improve confidence in the data new analysis could target existing sites with new proxies or new sites in under-represented regions.

Published global datasets from the MH (Hessler et al. 2014), LGM (Tierney et al., 2020) and Pliocene (McClymont & Ho et al., 2023) time slices were submitted to the Data Portal (WP7, Tasks 7.1 and 7.2) during the initial design work and will continue to be updated as new data emerges and as we interrogate the results. These MH, LGM and Pliocene datasets directly address Task 12.1, by reviewing existing global datasets of ocean circulation and ocean temperature at annual to millennial scales and updating these by adding newly published records, and SST records reconstructed using techniques not previously represented by past syntheses.

Figure 2: Compilation of published SST records (until January 2026), reconstructed using geochemical techniques and faunal assemblages, spanning the Mid-Holocene (6.5 - 5.5 ka).

Figure 3: Compilation of published SST records (until January 2026), reconstructed using geochemical techniques and faunal assemblages, spanning the LGM (23 - 19 ka).

Figure 4: Compilation of published (until January 2026) and emerging SST records reconstructed using geochemical techniques spanning the Pliocene (3.3-3 Ma).

2.3 Conclusion and possible impact

Published and new global datasets have been provided to the Data Portal (WP7). These datasets have been reviewed to confirm consistency in data reporting and to identify data quality indicators which can guide data-model comparison and model tuning for WP1, WP3 and WP4 within P2F. The databases include substantial new additions relative to previous global SST syntheses, particularly for the MH and LGM. Specifically, we add 251 new MH SST records beyond those compiled by Hessler et al. (2014), and 115 new LGM SST records on top of existing syntheses (Kucera et al., 2005a; Tierney et al., 2020), including, for the first time, many generated using newer geochemical proxies such as the Long-chain Diol Index, as well as previously uncompiled assemblage-based records. As a result, this represents the most up to date compilation in which all available SST records for the MH and LGM are brought together in a single, harmonised database, regardless of proxy type. In addition, 13 new Pliocene SST records have been added relative to previous syntheses (McClymont & Ho et al., 2023; Tierney et al., 2025). The datasets identify regions of the ocean where the addition of new proxy data will ensure that wherever possible multi-proxy reconstructions can be provided (e.g. NW Atlantic Ocean, North Pacific Ocean), to maximise data quality and to quantify data uncertainty. These insights are of benefit to P2F (e.g. for Tasks 12.2 and 12.3 and WP1, WP3 and WP4) but will also create benchmark datasets for international data-model comparison efforts (e.g. PMIP, PlioMIP).

Researchers requiring access to the latest version of the compilation should directly contact the lead authors. A streamlined, user-friendly version is being developed in collaboration with WP7 for the upcoming workshop in May 2026 (D7.1).

2.4 References

Barker, S., Cacho, I., Benway, H and Tachikawa, K. (2005). Planktonic foraminiferal Mg/Ca as a proxy for past oceanic temperatures: a methodological overview and data compilation for the Last Glacial Maximum. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 821-834.

- Barrows, T. T and Juggins, S. (2005). Sea-surface temperatures around the Australian margin and Indian Ocean during the Last Glacial Maximum. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 1017-1047.
- Comas-Bru, L., Rehfeld, K., Roesch, C., Amirnezhad-Mozhdehi, S., Harrison, S. P., Atsawawaranunt, K., et al. (2020). SISALv2: A comprehensive speleothem isotope database with multiple age–depth models. *Earth System Science Data*, 12(4), 2579–2606. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2579-2020>.
- Gao, Q., Capron, E., Sime, L. C., Rhodes, R. H., Sivankutty, R., Zhang, X., Otto-Bliesner, B. L., and Werner, M. (2025) Assessment of the southern polar and subpolar warming in the PMIP4 last interglacial simulations using paleoclimate data syntheses, *Climate of the Past*, 21, 419–440, <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-21-419-2025>.
- Gersonde, R., Crosta, X., Abelman, A and Armand, L. (2005). Sea-surface temperature and sea ice distribution of the Southern Ocean at the EPILOG Last Glacial Maximum—a circum-Antarctic view based on siliceous microfossil records. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 869-896.
- Hessler, I., Harrison, S.P., Kucera, M., Waelbroeck, C., Chen, M.-Te, Anderson, C., de Vernal, A., Fréchet, B., Cloke-Hayes, A., Leduc, G., Londeix, L. (2014): Implication of methodological uncertainties for mid-Holocene sea surface temperature reconstructions. *Climate of the Past*, 10(6), 2237-2252. <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-10-2237-2014>
- Kucera, M., Rosell-Mele, A., Schneider, R., Waelbroeck, C and Weinelt, M. (2005a). Multiproxy approach for the reconstruction of the glacial ocean surface (MARGO). *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 813–819.
- Kucera, M., Weinelt, M., Kiefer, T., Pflaumann, U., Hayes, A., Weinelt, M., Martin, Chen, M.-T., Mix, A.C., Barrows, T.T., Cortijo, E., Duprat, J., Juggins, S., Waelbroeck, C. (2005b). Reconstruction of sea-surface temperatures from assemblages of planktonic foraminifera: multi-technique approach based on geographically constrained calibration data sets and its application to glacial Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 951-998.
- Lunt, D.J., Otto-Bliesner, B.L., Brierley, C. et al. (2024) Paleoclimate data provide constraints on climate models' large-scale response to past CO₂ changes. *Commun Earth Environ* 5, 419. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01531-3>
- McClymont, E. L., & Ho, S. L., Ford, H. L., Bailey, I., Berke, M. A., Bolton, C. T., et al. (2023). Climate evolution through the onset and intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciation. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 61, e2022RG000793. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022RG000793>
- Meland, M.Y., Jansen, E and Elderfield, H. (2005) Constraints on SST estimates for the northern North Atlantic/Nordic Sea during the LGM. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 835-852.
- Ravelo, A. C. and Andreasen, D. H. (2000) Enhanced circulation during a warm period. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 27(7):1001–1004. <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/1999GL007000>.
- Rosell-Melé, A., Bard, E., Emeis, K.-C., Grieger, B., Hewitt, C., Müller, P.J and Schneider, R.R. (2004). Sea surface temperature anomalies in the oceans at the LGM estimated from the alkenone-U^K₃₇' index: comparison with GCMs. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 31, 1-4.
- Talley, L. D. (2003) Shallow, Intermediate, and Deep Overturning Components of the Global Heat Budget. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 33(3), 530–560.
- Tierney, J., Zhum J., King, J., Malevich, S.B., Hakim, G.J and Poulsen, C.J. 2020. Glacial cooling and climate sensitivity revisited. *Nature*, 584, 569–573. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2617-x>
- Tierney, J., King, J., Osman, M.B., Abell, J.T., Burls, N.J., Erfani, E., Cooper, V.T and Feng, R. 2025. Pliocene Warmth and Patterns of Climate Change Inferred From Paleoclimate Data Assimilation. *AGU Advances*, 6, e2024AV001356. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024AV001356>

3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of the results

3.1 Impact within the consortium

To ensure that our data compilation aligned closely with the needs of the Workstream 1 activities, particularly around the alignment of Workstream 1 time slice experiments and isotope-enabled model development, we have actively discussed our progress and plans with the modeling groups targeting the P2F time-slices:

- Attended the P2F kick-off meeting (Utrecht, March 2025) where we outlined our plans and discussed modeler needs including with Louise Sime (WP1) and Dan Lunt (WP3).
- Discussed requirements for the MH time slice with Louise Sime (WP1) and Pliocene time slice with Julia Tindall and Alan Haywood (WP3) at the European Geosciences Union General Assembly, 2025
- Contributed to data-model comparison and evaluation for stable-isotope enabled models (WP1) of the Last Interglacial and millennial-scale variability during the last glacial stage (see 3.2), led by Louise Sime and Irene Malmierca Vallet (WP1).
- Contributed to data-model comparison and evaluation for Atlantic circulation reconstructed for the mid-Pliocene warm period (see 3.2), including Julia Tindall and Alan Haywood (WP3).
- Presented our progress (oral) and contributed questions and feedback about the data portal (WP7) to the WS2 meeting which preceded the General Assembly (online, October 2025).
- Presented our progress (poster) to the P2F General Assembly (Utrecht, November 2025). Here, in the breakout sessions we were able to clarify the format of the data requirements for the WP Data Portal (including meta-data, quality control metrics, key target variables for ocean temperature and ocean circulation).

3.2 Impact within the wider scientific community

This deliverable enhances the scientific impact of P2F findings and strengthens research networks within the wider scientific community by providing a synthesis of the most up-to-date and quality-assessed ocean data for key time slices in the past that are directly relevant for paleoclimate modelers seeking data for testing or tuning, as well as paleoclimate proxy experts interested in understanding global-scale patterns of past climate change. It strengthens collaboration across proxy and model data communities by making available harmonized data sets with consistent and coherent quality control descriptors available for model tuning and data-model comparison which can be used in future studies beyond P2F.

Scientific Publications

<i>Title</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>Status (in prep, submitted, under review, accepted)</i>
Reconstructing Mid-Pliocene AMOC Dynamics Through Biogeochemical Proxy-Model Comparison	Duong Honbing Edmond, Heather Ford, Erin McClymont, Julia Tindall, Alan Haywood	Pending	In prep.
Synchronizing marine temperature records to study climate change in the past	T.D. Herbert, D. Evans, B. Hönisch, E.L. McClymont, M. Peral, J. Sepúlveda, K.K.	Pending	Accepted, PAGES Newsletter

	Śliwińska, V.E. Taylor		
H11 meltwater and standard 127 ka Last Interglacial simulations suggest more modest peak temperatures for both Greenland and Antarctica: a multi-model study of water isotopes	Sime, L.C., Sivankutty, R., Malmierca-Vallet, I., Goursaud Oger, S., LeGrande, A.N., McClymont, E.L., de Boer, A., Cauquoin, A. and Werner, M.	https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-21-1725-2025	Published, 2025

Other output

Type of activity (e.g. talk, poster, meeting etc.)	Details (where, who, what)	Target Audience + estimate on number of people reached	Impact Area
Poster	British Organic Geochemistry Society Annual Meeting 2025, Bristol, UK by Anna Cutmore “Past to Future: Defining the states and variability of the ocean”	Scientific Community; 120 people in attendance	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Poster	P2F General Assembly workshop 2025, Utrecht, the Netherlands by Anna Cutmore “Past to Future: Defining the states and variability of the ocean”	Scientific Community; 60 people in attendance	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Talk	European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria by Louise Sime (co-authors: Irene Malmierca Vallet, Erin McClymont)	Scientific Community; 100 people in attendance	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Conference session	Convened and chaired a conference session at the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2025 (“Feedbacks and Tipping Points: Unravelling the Past-to-Future Dynamics of Cryosphere-Climate Interactions”). Conveners: Irene Malmierca Vallet, Erin McClymont, Helle Astrid Kjær, Louise Sime.	Scientific Community; 100 people in attendance	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Talk	Ocean & Atmosphere Climate Dynamics Meeting, 2025, University College London, London, UK by Anna Cutmore “Past to Future: towards fully	Scientific Community; 30 people	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings

	palaeo-informed future climate projections”		
Talk	Department of Geography Seminar, 2025, Durham University, Durham, UK, by Anna Cutmore “Past to Future: Defining the states and variability of the ocean”	Scientific Community; 30 people	Strengthen research networks; Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings
Lecture	University of Durham, second year BSc Module “Reconstructing Environmental Change” Anna Cutmore, “Understanding Past Climate Change in the Mediterranean: From the Last Glacial to the present”	Future leaders; 50 people	Develop capacity in future leaders; Increase climate literacy
Lecture	University of Durham, final year BSc Module “Oceans and Climate Past and Present”. Erin McClymont, “Case Study: Warm Climates of the Past”	Future leaders; 50 people	Develop capacity in future leaders; Increase climate literacy

3.3 Impact beyond the scientific community

To build public trust in climate predictions, it is essential to show that the models we use today are capable of accurately simulating extreme changes. This deliverable bridges the gap between complex geology and the general public (e.g. school children and future policy makers) by demonstrating how Earth’s history serves as the ultimate "test track" for climate models. By providing accessible examples of how ancient ocean data validates current technology, we improve climate literacy and help students and future leaders understand why looking into the deep past is vital for understanding a changing future climate.

Activities

Type of activity (e.g. press release, social media, workshop etc.)	Details (where, who, what)	Target Audience + estimate on number of people reached	Impact Area
Presentation	Presentation to A-level science students at the James Allen’s Girls’ School in Dulwich, UK. “Time Travelling with Chemistry: How Molecules in Rocks and Oceans Reveal Earth’s Ancient Climate” Introducing how chemistry is used to reconstruct past climates and how this is useful for informing future climate change, highlighting the work of the P2F project.	General Public; 40 people in attendance	Increase climate literacy; Develop researcher’s skills in public engagement or policy

3.4 Future impact

Planned activity	Details (where, who, what)	Target Audience	Dissemination of outputs
Publication; Cutmore, A., McClymont, E., Sliwinska, K et al.	Publication of recommended SST records from the Mid-Holocene and LGM to be used by the modelling community for future ESMs	Scientific Community	Linkedin: share DOI along with layman abstract
Conference presentation; Cutmore, A., McClymont, E., Sliwinska, K.	“Past to Future: Defining the states and variability of the ocean” EGU 2026, Vienna, Austria	Scientific Community	Linkedin: share DOI to abstract and write a post about the event
Video	Short 3 minute video by Anna Cutmore, aimed at the general public, explaining in an understandable format, the findings of the research and its importance for better understanding future climate projections	General Public	Linkedin: share the video on WP12 researchers’ accounts

4. Changes with respect to the DoA (Description of Action)

None.